

Analysis of heat stress in classrooms of different school building types

Type of school building of the Grunderzeit Period: Oberschule "Kemmlerschule" in Plauen (Sachsen)

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Approach and goals

Climate change is leading to higher temperatures and more frequent heat waves, which is particularly dangerous for children under the age of 12. School classes are often in classrooms for more than six hours a day, which affects health, well-being and learning performance at high room temperatures. Since pupils can hardly influence the temperatures, they are particularly at risk. In addition, the school building stock is usually not designed for increasingly hot summers and tends to overheat anyway due to the large window areas of classrooms. The joint project KlimaKonform II therefore investigated how high the heat load is in classrooms of different school building types in Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt and Thuringia and which heat adaptation measures are particularly effective.

This study uses a combined approach to analyze heat stress and thermal comfort in seven schools. These include three schools from the Grunderzeit period (1870–1918) in Plauen, Dresden and Gera, two prefabricated schools (1970–1990) in Zeitz and Dresden, a school from the post-war period (1952) in Dresden and a newly built school, also in Dresden. The comparison can be used to determine which building types are particularly susceptible to extreme heat stress.

This profile reports on the results on heat stress and thermal comfort in the type of school building of the Grunderzeit period, based on the secondary school "Kemmlerschule" in Plauen (Saxony).

The analysis follows the process shown in the diagram below and consists of several steps:

- **Step a: Selection of representative school buildings**
- **Step B: Temperature measurements in classrooms**
Continuous measurement of classroom and outdoor temperatures from June to the end of September 2024 in two classrooms per school.
- **Step C: Survey of pupils and teachers on the perceived heat stress**
At the same time, pupils and their teachers in the two classrooms per school were asked how they felt about the indoor climate in summer. The survey makes it possible to record temperature-dependent well-being.
- **Step D: Effectiveness analysis of heat adaptation via thermal building simulation**

In addition, detailed 3D models of the examined classrooms were created for thermal building simulations. In this way, the effectiveness of different adaptation measures can be tested and compared in simulations.

Linking these steps (a to d) ensures that both objectively measured and subjectively perceived aspects of thermal comfort are taken into account.

This profile focuses mainly on structural-technical and behavioural adaptation to reduce heat stress in classrooms. The equally relevant school organisational measures (location of the summer holiday period, shortened lessons, switching to cooler classrooms) and schoolyard design aspects are not the subject of this profile.

Oberschule Kemmlerschule in Plauen (Sachsen)

a General information about the school

Description

The Kemmlerschule is a secondary school in the town of Plauen, Saxony, Germany. The school was founded in 1902 and is an example of a typical school building of the Wilhelminian period with thick brick walls, wooden beam ceilings and large windows. The windows are double-glazed without solar control glazing. The classrooms do not have external sun protection, but they do have internal glare protection. The classrooms studied are oriented to the northwest and southeast.

Source: Google Earth, 04/2018

Sources: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2021

General information

Type of school	High School
Construction type	Gründerzeit
Address	Fiedlerstraße 3 08527 Plauen
Status of the renovation	Unrenovated
Grade levels taken into account	8th and 9th grade

Classroom Northwest Façade (Room 32)

Window details	Floor space	62,8 m²
	Orientation of the windows	Nord-West
	Window glazing	Double glazing (no solar control glazing))
	Shading	Only internal glare protection (no external sun protection)
	Ventilation	Windows that can be opened
	Exterior wall	44 cm thick brick walls
	Interior wall	60 cm thick brick walls
	Ceiling	Wooden beam ceiling

Classroom South-East Façade (Room 33)

Window details	Floor space	62,8 m²
	Orientation of the windows	South-East
	Window glazing	Double glazing (no solar control glazing)
	Shading	Only internal glare protection (no external sun protection)
	Ventilation	Windows that can be opened
	Exterior wall	Brick walls
	Interior wall	Brick walls
	Ceiling	Wooden beam ceiling

Oberschule Kemmlerschule in Plauen (Sachsen)

b Survey of pupils on heat stress

General Information Pupils from two classrooms were asked about their perception of heat stress on four different days. Room 32 is used by 8th grade students, while Room 33 is used by 9th grade students. On a typical summer day (survey date: August 28, 2024), 22 people in room 32 and 6 people in room 33 took part in the survey. On the hot survey day (August 14, 2024), 19 students were present in room 32 and 5 in room 33. It should be noted that the survey is not statistically significant if the number of participants in a room during the survey is less than 10.

Source: Christoph Schünemann, 06/2024

Summer Day (28.08.2024)

Room 32 at 09:30		Room 33 at 09:30	
Outdoor	17,8 °C	Outdoor	17,8 °C
Indoor	24,6 °C	Indoor	28 °C

The values in the pie chart show the number of responses in each class on the day of the survey.

*Number of respondents 10

Pie charts to compare the temperatures perceived by the students in both classrooms: on a typical summer day (left) and on a hot day (right).

On a typical summer day (left), most of the students found room 32 okay. On a hot day, more students also felt uncomfortable in room 32. Room 33 cannot be evaluated due to the small number of participants.

The reported feeling of fatigue was similar in both rooms on both days.

Hot day (14.08.2024)

Room 32 at 9:30		Room 33 at 9:30	
Outdoor	23,8 °C	Outdoor	23,8 °C
Indoor	27,9 °C	Indoor	31 °C

Measures taken during the survey

Room 32: Ventilation through open window
Room 33: Cross ventilation through open door and window

Room 32: Ventilation through open window
Room 33: Ventilation through open window

Conclusion

The perceived heat stress in both classrooms is significantly more critical on a hot day than on a summer day, which is reflected both in the temperature perception and in the well-being. On the hot day, room 32 was 31 °C due to the south-east orientation of the windows, in contrast to the north-west orientation for room 33 (28 °C). It is noteworthy that these high room temperatures occur at an outside temperature of 24 °C. This indicates that more windows should possibly be opened to cool down the classrooms.

Oberschule Kemmlerschule in Plauen (Sachsen)

c Temperature measurements and simulations in the classroom

Outdoor temperature measurement with KLIPS sensor

- Outside temperature
- School operations

The outside temperature for the summer of 2024 was measured with a KLIPS temperature sensor in the schoolyard. The graph shows the outside temperature curve from August 5 to September 11, 2024. This study period was characterized by extreme heat, with 9 hot days (maximum outside temperature above 30 °C), 2 tropical nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 20 °C) and 6 warm nights (minimum outside temperature at night above 18 °C).

Classroom interior measurements

- School operations
- Temperature in the room 32
- Room temperature 33
- Outside temperature

Between August 5 and September 11, 2024, classroom 33 exceeded the critical room temperature of 30 °C 19 times and room 32 only 1 time. However, both exceeded the comfort temperature of 26 °C almost continuously, with room 33 exceeding it more often than room 32. The maximum temperature for room 33 reaches 33 °C, for room 32 it is just over 30 °C. Due to its south-east orientation and the lack of sufficient sun protection, room 33 is significantly more heat-stressed than room 32.

Thermal building simulations of the current state (Room 33)

3-dimensional model of the both classrooms in the thermal building simulation

The comparison of the simulated room temperature curve with the measured room temperature curve in the actual state is satisfactory using the local climate and the assumption that in the period from 8:00 to 14:00 (weekdays) a window and the classroom door are open if the outside temperature is less than the room temperature and two more windows are opened every 10 minutes for fresh air supply (regardless of the room temperature).

Oberschule Kemmlerschule in Plauen (Sachsen)

d Effectiveness of heat adaptation measures and recommendations

Effectiveness of adaptation measures to reduce heat stress

Simulations of measures for heat adaptation

The bar diagram shows the overtemperature degree hours (ÜTG) for different simulation variants of both classrooms. The ÜTG are an indication of how many hours and how much the comfort temperature of 26 °C per year (Kh/a) is exceeded in the classroom. While v0 represents the reference (actual state) of the room, the other variants show the following differences:

- Significant reduction of the ÜTG in room 33 with external window shading (V1).
- High effectiveness of solar control glazing to reduce heat stress (v1)
- The operation of a possible automatic window ventilation during the day and at night is also very effective in cooling the rooms at night with the cool outside air (v4).

Temperature curves of classroom 33 for different variants

The temperature curve for room 33 on the left also illustrates the above results. With external shading, which the rooms of the school building do not have, the heat load is about 4 °C lower.

Recommendations

The measurements, surveys, simulations and comparison with the classrooms of other school buildings lead to the following assessment and recommendation regarding the reduction of heat stress:

In the Kemmlerschule, classrooms on the south-east side (street side) in particular are heavily heat-laden, with temperatures of up to 33 °C. This is mainly due to the large window areas of the classrooms with older double glazing, which have a high total energy transmittance for solar radiation. Replacing the windows with solar control glazing would lead to a significant reduction in heat stress. External shading is even more effective, which is challenging with the arched windows and monument protection requirements, but there are also visually appealing solutions for this. In the room temperature measurements, it was noticed that very high room temperatures above 30 °C occurred even at cool outside temperatures. This is a clear sign that cooling rooms by opening many windows still has high potential, which was also shown by the building simulations. A combination of structural and technical measures together with adapted behaviour and school organisational measures can significantly reduce heat stress in classrooms.

General recommendations, derived from the comparison of the school buildings examined, can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19651356>